

RESULTS OF THE WORKING CONDITIONS OF WORKERS IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES.

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Resume.

In this paper, we investigate the oral cavity state, its pathological processes and the impact of environmental factors which industrial workers deal with. The influence of operating conditions on the incidence of dental diseases is considered. We revealed the dependence of caries occurrence and development of periodontal tissue pathology on the industrial environment conditions, work experience, and implementation of preventive measures by dentists.

Keywords: dental caries, periodontal pathology, incidencerate, professional pathology, metrogil-denta.

Relevance In the process of intensive industrial development, studying the role of harmful and health-related factors in the working environment is timely and very important.

Workers at industrial enterprises are exposed to the combined action of many unfavorable factors in the working environment, causing a decrease in the body's resistance and an increase in the incidence of periodontal tissue pathology [Buchmann R., 2001; Kottgen Chr., Ernst Cl.-P., Willishausen B., 2001]. Materials and research methods As a result of the introduction of new high-performance equipment in the lye-winding industry "TEXTILE FINANCE KHOREZM", production noise has become of great importance as one of the harmful production factors, as well as the dustiness of the air in working rooms in various workshops and the most important harmful production factors are microclimatic conditions, characterized in the warm season as heating due to the operation of steaming machines.

Result and discussion

Studies have shown that the noise intensity during operation of automatic rewinding and coco-winding machines reaches up to 90 dBA. A comparison of actual noise levels at workplaces with permissible sound pressure levels showed that coco-winding machines generate noise that exceeds the permissible level by 5-10 dBA. Industrial noise is constant, broadband, level 86-93 dBA, maximum at frequencies 800-1200 Hz [Khabibova.N.N., Kurbonova.2020: Kobilova G.A. et al., 2020].

Conclusions

The air dust content of working premises in various workshops ranges from 5.0 to 20 mg/m³ with a maximum permissible concentration of 6 mg/m³, while the main source of dust content in the air is dry cocoons.

Industrial lighting in accordance with the current KMK 2.01.05-98 of the Republic of Uzbekistan in workplaces should be 300 lux with general lighting and 1000 lux with combined artificial lighting. The actual illumination of workshops ranges from 100 to 300 lux.

A complex of harmful industrial hygienic factors in industrial production can have a certain impact on the functional state of the body of workers and on their morbidity, including dental disease.

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